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Submitted Via Electronic Mail: Blake.D.Barrett@ice.dhs.gov, ICESustainability@ice.dhs.gov

MEMORANDUM

DATE: September 4, 2025

TO: Blake Barrett, Program Manager Southeast, Tactical Communications, U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement

FROM: Lourdes Mena, Field Supervisor, Caribbean Ecological Services Field Office

SUBJECT: Biological Opinion for the Proposed Mona Island Telecommunications Project at Mona Island, Puerto Rico.

This document transmits the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's (Service) biological opinion (BO) based on our review of the Department of Homeland Security's United States Immigration and Customs Enforcement (ICE) proposed Mona Island Telecommunications project and its effects on the threatened Mona boa (*Chilabothrus monensis*; currently listed as *Epicrates monensis monensis*) and threatened Higo chumbo cactus (*Harrisia portoricensis*) in accordance with section 7 of the Endangered Species Act (Act) of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 et seq.). Your April 29, 2025, letter requesting formal consultation was received on April 30, 2025.

This BO is based on information provided in the draft Biological Assessment (BA) dated June 27, 2025, draft Environmental Assessment (EA) dated April 30, 2025, and other information in our files. According to the BA, the proposed actions are likely to adversely affect the Mona boa and the Higo chumbo cactus.

This BO considers the effects of the project Actions on these species. The following are listed species and critical habitat that also occur on Mona Island in which effects from this project were evaluated and the Service concurs with a "not likely to adversely affect" determination: Hawksbill sea turtle (*Eretmochelys imbricata*) and its critical habitat, Green sea turtle (*Chelonia mydas*), Leatherback sea turtle (*Dermochelys coriacea*), Loggerhead sea turtle (*Caretta caretta*), and the Mona ground iguana (*Cyclura stejnegeri*). The BA also determined no effects on the Yellow-shouldered blackbird (*Agelaius xanthomus*) and its critical habitat, the Roseate tern (*Sterna dougallii dougallii*), and the Black-capped petrel (*Pterodroma hasitata*).

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

1. Description of the Proposed Action

This project seeks to demolish and replace the existing telecommunications infrastructure on Mona Island, a subtropical island located approximately 42 miles (67.6 km) off the west coast of Puerto Rico and managed as a Nature Reserve by the Puerto Rico Department of Natural and Environmental Resources (DNER). The entire project will be approximately 10 terrestrial acres (4 ha) and 1 square nautical mile (3.43 square km). The terrestrial portion of the project area will be adjacent to Sardinera Beach and the Sardinera Anchorage Inlet. The marine portion of the project area will extend from the coast of Sardinera Beach out 1.3 nautical miles (2.41 km) into the Mona Passage and will include the nearshore coral reefs.

Under the Proposed Action, ICE will obtain a sub-lease to the U.S. Coast Guard's (USCG's) lease with the Puerto Rico DNER for the use of the land for the Proposed Action. The lease will allow ICE to complete demolition and construction work throughout the duration of the Proposed Action, as well as future maintenance work on the new telecommunications system. ICE will also enter into a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with DNER to determine project details and logistics that are agreeable to both parties for the duration of the Proposed Action and the subsequent operation and maintenance of the new infrastructure.

ICE will remove and dispose of the existing inadequate telecommunications tower, equipment shelter, solar PV system, equipment buildings, and associated equipment from Mona Island to Puerto Rico. ICE will then install a new 150-ft (46 m) self-supporting telecommunications tower, two self-contained prefabricated equipment shelters, and a new solar PV array field. The new telecommunications tower and equipment shelter will be in the footprint of the existing solar PV array. The new solar PV array and battery shelter will be located below the cliff, northeast of the Visitor Center and southwest of the new tower. All of the new equipment will be hurricane-rated to withstand at least 125 mile per hour (mph) (201 kilometer per hour [km/h]) winds.

Demolition and construction activities include the use of a heavy lift helicopter, sonic drill rigs, skid steers, metal saws, and other hand tools. The work plan also includes the use of a large and small barge, which will be utilized to transport project materials and personnel from San Juan to Mona Island. The barges will be anchored beyond the offshore coral reefs, and materials will be unloaded using the heavy lift helicopter. In the event of inclement weather including high winds in which the helicopter could not fly, a small, single-container vessel will be utilized to deliver materials from the barges to the existing boat dock.

The project area or action area (AA) will be divided into six separate operational zones, which are described below per the BA and EA, in addition to other areas described outside of these zones. To implement the Proposed Action, ICE is proposing a phased work plan from December 2025 to March 2026. A description of the phases is also provided below per the BA and EA.

Zone descriptions:

- Zone 1 - Beach Landing: Located on Sardinera Beach, this zone will only be utilized in

the event of inclement weather for offloading project materials including small equipment, large vehicles, heavy equipment, bulk materials, and personnel from the barges. The beach landing zone will be approximately 2 acres (0.81 ha), including 0.50 acres (0.20 ha) of coastline and 1.50 acres (0.61 ha) of marine area. No land or vegetation clearing will be necessary in this zone for the Project. Transport of equipment on this zone will include the use of ramps and mats to protect the beach during transport.

- Zone 2 - Helicopter landing: This zone is approximately 0.63 acres (0.25 ha) for the helicopter refueling and to unload and load material for transport to and from the tower site (Zone 5). In addition to a helicopter, a fueling truck will remain within Zone 2 for the Project's duration. No land or vegetation clearing will be necessary in this zone for the Project, and the land in this zone has been previously disturbed.
- Zone 3 - Buffer and Staging zone: Buffer zone for temporarily staging equipment and materials between the beach landing zone and the tower site. This zone will ensure a smooth flow of materials, prevent congestion in critical zones, and will primarily be used during active transport times. Materials staged in this area may include storage containers, steel tower components, concrete, aggregate, water, solar panels, cabling, or antennas. Zone 3 will be approximately 0.70 acres (0.28 ha). No land or vegetation clearing will be necessary in this zone for the Project, and the land in this zone has been previously disturbed.
- Zone 4 - Barracks and Adjacent Structures: Temporary barracks accommodations and operational support for up to 10 personnel with an approximate size of 2.50 acres (1.01 ha). Facilities include sleeping quarters; kitchens; sanitary services including portable toilets, showers, and water purification systems; solar-powered electrical systems with backup generators; and a communication hub for coordination between zones and reporting. No land or vegetation clearing will be necessary in this zone for the Project, and the land in this zone has been previously disturbed.
- Zone 5 - Tower Site: This site includes the demolition and new construction area for the telecommunication tower and new equipment shelter. The new tower and equipment shelter will be constructed within the current footprint of the existing solar PV array. Most of the proposed tower site, which totals approximately 0.32 acres (0.13 ha), has been previously disturbed. A total of 0.04 acre (0.016 ha) of vegetated area will be cleared for a temporary staging area at this zone during construction but allowed to return to natural conditions following construction.
- Zone 6 - Solar Array Site and Battery Shelter: Site for new solar PV array (100 panels) which consists of approximately 0.02 acres (0.01 ha) on an existing concrete slab (i.e., basketball court). Less than 0.01 acre (0.004 ha) of sparse vegetation cover will need to be cleared. The foundation for the battery equipment shelter will also require a 0.003-acre (0.001 ha) area to be cleared of sparse vegetation. The location of the battery shelter will be verified pre-construction and is dependent on the terms of the MOU between ICE and DNER. The final location will be no more than 50 ft from the new solar PV array.

- Conduit: There will be ground disturbance and vegetation clearing for the installation of buried conduit and wiring, at a depth of approximately 3 ft (0.91 m) below grade to connect the solar PV array to the battery shelter in Zone 6, while overhead wiring will connect the battery shelter to the new tower site (Zone 5) to minimize drilling into the bedrock. Clearing and disturbance in Zone 6 will be in areas that have been previously disturbed in the Sardinera camp from previous constructions and access roads.
- Anchor area of barges: A large and a small ocean barge will anchor on a sandy bottom beyond the reef edge offshore from Sardinera Beach.

Phase descriptions:

Phase 0 - Large Ocean Barge Transit and Arrival: A large ocean barge will depart from San Juan to Mona Island and transport equipment and vehicles such as fuel trucks, skid steers and drill rigs. Barge will have the minimum lighting needed to comply with navigation regulations and best safety practices (not specified) will be used during night hours while anchored. A heavy lift CH-47 helicopter will transport the large materials from the barge to the Tower Site (Zone 5). In cases where the helicopter can't be used a small, single container vessel will be directed to the beach landing Zone 1. Zone 2 and 3 will also be used during this Phase 0.

- Phase 1 - Mobilization and Staging: This phase will include 15 trips of a small ocean barge from San Juan to Mona Island. This small barge will also comply with minimal lighting regulations and the CH-47 heavy lift helicopter will also transport equipment from the small barge to Zones 3 and 5. In cases where the helicopter can't be used a small, single container vessel will be used to transport the equipment to the existing dock or to the beach landing Zone 1. To demarcate active construction areas and restrict access, temporary construction tape and signs will be installed in Zones 5 and 6. Tape and signs will be removed duration Phase 5.
- Phase 2 - Site Demolition and Preparation: This phase will include demolition of the existing tower and foundation, guy wires and anchors, equipment shelter and buildings and solar PV system all in Zone 5. The guy wires will be cut, and the tower will then be allowed to fall in as controlled a manner as possible. The heavy lift helicopter will be used to airlift and remove the old tower and project equipment. A Bobcat mini excavator (or similar) will be used for site preparation, an area of approximately 0.03 acres (0.012 ha). The area with the current solar PV system will be graded and leveled for a new tower and shelter foundation using hand tools and a skid steer. A total of 0.04 acre (0.016 ha) of vegetated area will be cleared for a temporary staging area in Zone 5 as well but allowed to return to natural conditions following construction.
- Phase 3 - Foundation Construction and Energy Setup (i.e., conduit and wiring installation): This phase will include construction of the foundation and rebar installation at Zone 5 for the new tower and equipment shelter, on Zone 6 for the new solar PV array and battery shelter and followed by concrete pouring for the foundations. Rock anchors will be installed to a depth of 75 ft (23 m) using a skid steer and sonic drill.

This phase also includes set up and installation of the new hurricane-rated solar PV array (100 panels) with a helical anchoring system. This installation will occur in an area previously disturbed area and will require minimal clearing of less than 0.01 acres (0.0004 ha) of sparse vegetation. The foundation for the battery equipment shelter will also require a 0.003-acre (0.001 hectare) area to be cleared of sparse vegetation.

This phase also includes the use of hand tools and skid steer to clear the vegetation for the buried conduit and wiring. The conduit and wire will be installed approximately 3 ft (0.91 m) below grade on the beach, while overhead wiring will connect the battery shelter to the new tower to minimize drilling into bedrock. Some wiring along existing trails may be buried, and the final wiring installation plan will be verified prior to construction and coordinated with DNER.

- Phase 4 - Tower Construction and Shelter Installation: During this phase, tower sections will be airlifted via the helicopter to Zone 5 and assembled, followed by construction of the new 150-ft (46 m) tower. The shelters will be approximately 130 square feet (sq ft) (12 square meters [sq m]) each; the battery shelter will hold power and battery equipment, and the equipment shelter will house radiofrequency equipment, including antennas and transmission lines.
- Phase 5: Finalization and Demobilization: Once all new infrastructure is complete, this phase includes load testing and system inspections. The temporary tape and signs will be removed as well as all other equipment associated with the previous system. Materials will be properly disposed of at approved recycling facilities or an approved landfill.
- Maintenance activity: ICE will require access to the project area twice a year following project completion for routine maintenance. No construction work is anticipated during these routine site visits, but necessary equipment repairs may be performed. Helicopters and boats will be utilized to travel to Mona Island for maintenance activities. The new solar panels and solar panel mounts will have a lifespan of 25 years. The tower's exact lifespan is undetermined but will exceed that of the solar panels with regular maintenance.

Conservation Measures:

The following conservation measures were specified in the BA and additional information provided by ICE on the use of the helicopter:

- Best Management Practices (BMPs) will be implemented during the construction and operation of the project to minimize potential adverse effects to federally listed species. Designated no-work zones will be established in areas known for wildlife activity to prevent disruption. These zones will be marked on all project maps, and personnel will be briefed to avoid interference. Construction and transport activities will be scheduled to reduce noise, especially during critical wildlife activity periods such as dawn and dusk. Vehicles will observe maximum speed limits to minimize the possibility of wildlife

collisions. Staging and stockpile areas will be located within or immediately adjacent to the construction footprint to reduce the area of habitat disturbance.

- A qualified biologist will conduct nocturnal surveys of the project area and the general vicinity for Mona boas for at least three nights prior to the start of project activities. If individuals are observed on branches or equipment in the project area, the boas will be removed by the biologist using recommended practices, which include transporting boas in burlap bags or other secured containers and relocating to suitable forested habitat at least 0.6 mi (1 km) from the project site.
- A qualified biologist will survey the project area to determine if any cacti are present onsite, including adults, juveniles, and seedlings. If any Higo chumbo are observed in temporary staging areas, the location of the cacti will be communicated to project personnel, and a buffer will be established to prevent the storage of equipment and foot traffic near the cacti. If cacti are identified on sites where vegetation will be cleared, consultation will be initiated with the Service and the DNER to determine how to best limit adverse effects to the cacti, which may include shifting the project footprint to avoid the cacti. If ICE determines that the project footprint cannot be shifted to avoid any Higo chumbo present, the cacti could be damaged, destroyed, or potentially relocated.
- Construction and operation of the proposed action will follow the USFWS Migratory Bird Program's recommended BMPs for communications tower projects (USFWS 2021) and the Federal Communications Commission guidance to reduce bird collisions with communications towers (FCC 2017). The Service recommends that towers do not exceed 199 ft (60.6 m). Additionally, because the tower would be self-supporting, no guy wires would be needed, thus reducing the risk of collisions compared to the existing tower. Furthermore, the red light on top of the new tower would flash, reducing bird collisions compared to steady-burning lights. Finally, security lighting would be motion-sensitive, down-shielded, and minimum-intensity to limit nighttime bird attraction (FCC 2017).
- A qualified biologist would conduct a nest survey in the areas to be cleared no more than 5 days prior to the start of construction (USFWS 2021). If any black-capped petrel or Yellow-shouldered blackbird nests are observed in these areas, consultation would be initiated with the Service and DNER, and a buffer zone would be established around any nest that is found; no activities would occur within the buffer zone until nestlings have fledged.
- No permanent structures would be built on or near the beach as part of the project and therefore the proposed action would not permanently modify the beach habitat. ICE will follow the recommended conservation measures for sea turtles in Puerto Rico (USFWS 2022) for the duration of the project. These include sea turtle nest surveys among other measures to avoid potential detrimental effects on sea turtle, their nests and nesting habitat. Modifications to beach topography resulting from the proposed project would be restored at the end of each day through raking, filling holes, and smoothing out sand to allow use by turtles. Actions on the beach would only occur during daytime hours, and materials and equipment would be removed from the beach at night to minimize

disturbance to potential nesting turtles. Night workers would use portable red light-emitting diode (LED) lights in all active zones to minimize disruption to nesting turtles.

- Proposed actions would occur outside of the June to November breeding season of the Mona iguana. Furthermore, a qualified biologist would survey the areas intended for demolition and clearing for Mona iguana burrows. If Mona iguana burrows are observed in these areas, the location of the burrow would be immediately communicated to project personnel, and a buffer zone would be established around the burrow; no activities would occur within the buffer zone for the duration of the project. Additional consultation would be initiated with the Service and DNER.
- To minimize environmental impact during helicopter airlift operations in remote or sensitive ecosystems, the following standard procedures are employed as needed: establishment of exclusion zones surrounding lift areas to protect flora, fauna, and ground personnel; use of netting or geotextile fabric to stabilize vegetation in fragile areas; deployment of water trucks or misting systems for dust control where feasible; flight path planning to avoid direct overflight of protected zones or ecological features. These practices have been used successfully on similar missions and can be adjusted further based on site-specific coordination with environmental representatives.

2. Status and Environmental Baseline of the Species and Critical Habitat

The Mona boa is a non-venomous snake endemic to Mona Island that was listed as threatened species in 1978 and Mona Island designated as critical habitat (43 FR 4618). Mona boas are considered mostly nocturnal and semi-arboreal and found in most habitats on Mona Island (USFWS 2020). Although current population numbers or trends for the Mona boa are unknown, its population has been roughly estimated at a density of about 120 snakes per hectare in suitable boa habitat (Tolson 2000) and is probably more abundant than previously thought (Tolson 2007). This species has a low detection probability due to its cryptic behavior and inactivity while sheltering. The main threat is feral cat predation, while threats to habitat include habitat modification from feral pigs and goats (USFWS 2020).

Higo chumbo is a columnar cactus listed as a threatened species in 1990 (55 FR 32252). Higo chumbo is historically known from one area on the main island of Puerto Rico and from three offshore islands off the west coast of Puerto Rico: Mona and Monito Islands managed by the Puerto Rico Department of Natural Environmental Resources (DNER), and Desecheo Island National Wildlife Refuge (NWR). The most recent density estimate for the Higo chumbo population in Mona Island is 0.001 cactus per square meter for a population estimate of approximately 59,000 individuals (Rojas-Sandoval and Meléndez-Ackerman 2013); about 136 individuals in Monito Island (USFWS 2023); and at least 43 in Desecheo NWR (IC 2018). The species is considered extirpated in Puerto Rico. Main threats include disease and predation (Factor C) due to insect pests, predation and trampling by feral invasive goats and pigs, and by natural stressors (Factor E) such as competition with invasive grasses, direct and indirect hurricane impacts, and a restricted distribution as well as low population numbers (USFWS 2023).

3. Effects of the Action on Listed Species and Critical Habitat and Cumulative Effects

In a BO for a listed species, the effects of the proposed action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it will not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action (50 CFR 402.02).

We identified and described the activities included in the proposed Action under Section I of this BO. Our analyses of the consequences caused by each of these activities follows.

3.1. Use of heavy lift helicopter CH-47

Change Caused by the Activity: This change may cause a temporary disturbance of the habitat within and around Zone 5. According to information provided by ICE the flight/hover height of the helicopter is typically 200 to 300 feet above ground level during lift activities and specified that this height maintains safe standoff from sensitive terrain, reduces surface disturbance from rotor wash, and aligns with best practices in ecologically fragile environments. In addition, the helicopter would result in elevated noise levels between 96 dBA during flight to 115 dBA when taking off and landing.

Exposure to the Change: We expect all Mona boas and Higo chumbo cactus to be exposed at any time within the Zones used by this activity, particularly in Zone 5. Per the information provided, an estimated area of exposure from the rotor wash is up to 300 feet in radius from the lift point, with the strongest exposure occurring directly beneath the helicopter. In addition, the maximum rotor wash velocity at ground level is approximately 80 mph, winds considered equivalent to a Category 1 hurricane (<https://www.nhc.noaa.gov/aboutsshws.php>). Exposure to sound would be highest during taking off and landing which is limited to Zone 2.

Consequences Resulting from Exposure: Consequences include, mostly in Zones 2 and 5: (1) temporary modification of the habitat; (2) permanent effects to habitat as large branches may snap and shallow rooted trees may be toppled; (3) potential loss and/or injury to Higo chumbo cactus that may not sustain this change. Consequences will occur within previously disturbed and undisturbed habitat. Per the information provided, project actions will include standard protocols to minimize impacts during airlift operations.

3.2. Transport, demolition, vegetation clearance, and construction activities

Change Caused by the Activity: This activity will modify the existing conditions and habitat at tower site in Zone 5 due to the removal and grading of the existing tower site and vegetation clearance of 0.04 acres (0.016 ha) that will be allowed to revegetate after construction. Activity includes the use of a heavy lift CH-47 helicopter to transport equipment and materials to and from the work zones and hand tools, skid steer, mini excavator, drill rigs, among other equipment to complete the work. Phase 3 of the project includes vegetation clearance and ground disturbance as well to install the buried conduit and wiring. The conduit and wire will be

installed approximately 3 ft (0.91 m) below grade on Zone 6, while overhead wiring will connect the battery shelter to the new tower (Zone 5) to minimize drilling into the bedrock.

The activity may cause injury and/or mortality to any Mona boa individuals that may be present within the project zones, particularly in Zone 5 and along the conduit that will connect with the battery shelter in Zone 6. In addition, this activity will most likely result in the cutting (i.e., injury and mortality) of any Higo chumbo cactus that may be present within the project zones. There is also the potential for the introduction of invasive pests such as the *Harrisia* cactus mealybug (*Hypogecoccus pungens*) that would be detrimental to the cactus populations in Mona Island.

Exposure to the Change: We expect all Mona boas and Higo chumbo cactus to be exposed at any time during the proposed activity, particularly in Zone 5 and along the conduit path that goes down towards Zone 6 to connect with the battery shelter.

Consequences Resulting from Exposure: Consequences include: (1) a permanent and temporary modification and loss of habitat in Zones 5 and 6 and along the conduit connections; (2) small reduction in population size with the potential loss and/or injury of Mona boas and Higo chumbo cactus; (3) potential relocation of Mona boas from the work area into suitable habitat; and (4) potential introduction of harmful insect pests that may have significant detrimental effects on the Higo chumbo population in Mona Island. Relocation of Mona boas should not have long term consequences on the species and overall status of the population. Consequences will occur within previously disturbed and undisturbed habitat. Project actions will include terms and conditions to minimize effects on these species.

3.3. Critical Habitat

The entire Mona Island (14033 acres [5679 ha]) is designated critical habitat for the Mona boa, excluding “those existing man-made structures or settlements which are not necessary to the normal needs or survival of the species” (43 FR 4618). Although the project area overlaps this critical habitat for the Mona boa, most of the 10 acre (4 ha) terrestrial project area has been previously disturbed (i.e., Sardinera camp area and existing tower footprint) and most of the habitat for this species will not be modified by the proposed actions. The previously disturbed tower site (Zone 5) is approximately 0.32 acres (0.13 ha) of which 0.04 acres (0.016 ha) of undisturbed habitat will be cleared for a temporary staging area and allowed to return to natural conditions after the completion of the project.

3.4. Cumulative effects on the listed species

The Mona boa is endemic species only found on Mona Island. Thus, the status of this species and environmental baseline considers effects along both the entire range of these species and the action area for this project. Although the Higo chumbo cactus also occurs in another two offshore islands (Monito and Desecheo), effects are only considered on Mona Island which harbors the largest and most important population for this species. In its request for consultation, ICE did not describe, and the Service is not aware of, any future non-Federal activities that are reasonably certain to occur in relation to this project on Mona Island. Therefore, we do not

anticipate cumulative effects that we must consider in formulating our opinion for these actions.

4. Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the Mona boa and Higo chumbo cactus, Mona boa critical habitat, the environmental baseline for the AA, the effects of the proposed action and cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the action, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the Mona boa and the Higo chumbo cactus, and is not likely to adversely modify designated critical habitat for the Mona boa.

The Service reached these conclusions because:

- A. Most of the proposed project will occur within the footprint of previously disturbed and developed areas.
- B. Avoidance and minimization measures were developed in coordination with the Service for that purpose and will be implemented in coordination with the Service and DNER.
- C. Adverse impacts (including those that conform to incidental take) are likely to be small in magnitude, short-term and geographically localized in relation to the amount of habitat available for the Mona boa and Higo chumbo cactus in Mona Island.
- D. The project will not cause a permanent net loss of habitat, net loss of habitat function, net loss of critical habitat or a net loss of functional value of critical habitat.
- E. The amount or extent of incidental take of listed species is unlikely to have adverse population-level impacts to the Mona boa or Higo chumbo, particularly with the implementation of appropriate conservation measures.
- F. ICE and DNER will complete a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) to determine project details and logistics that are agreeable to both parties for the duration of the Proposed Action and the subsequent operation of the new infrastructure.

5. Incidental Take Statement

ESA §9(a)(1) and regulations issued under §4(d) prohibit the take of endangered and threatened fish and wildlife species without special exemption. The term "take" in the ESA means "to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture, or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct" (ESA §3(19)).

Under the terms of ESA §7(b)(4) and §7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to a Federal agency action that would not violate ESA §7(a)(2) is not considered prohibited, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement (ITS).

The Actions considered in this BO include terms and conditions to avoid and minimize impacts as outlined in Section 2 of this document. This includes the capture and relocation of boas found on the AA, and which are in harm's way. Because the capture and relocation of boas is the result of an otherwise lawful action, such capture and relocation are considered incidental take, and no section 10a1A permit for such capture and relocation is required.

Through this statement, the Service exempts take from this Action as described and

contemplated by this BO from being considered prohibited take under section 9, and includes an exception to the prohibitions against trapping, capturing, or collecting listed species.

For the exemption in ESA §7(o)(2) to apply to the Action considered in this BO, the Federal Agency and the Recipient must undertake the non-discretionary Reasonable and Prudent Measure, and their Terms and Conditions described below. Consistent with ESA section 7(b)(4)(C)(iv), the Federal Agency and the Recipient has a continuing duty to regulate the Action activities covered by this ITS. The Federal Agency is responsible for the Action activities covered by this ITS that are under its control and are not under their jurisdiction. The protective coverage of §7(o)(2) may lapse if the Federal Agency and the Recipient fails to:

- assume and implement the terms and conditions; or
- require a permittee, contractor, or grantee to adhere to the terms and conditions of the ITS through enforceable terms that are added to the permit, contract, or grant document.

In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, ICE must report the progress of the Action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in this Sections 5.1 and 5.2 of this BO.

This section specifies the amount or extent of take of listed wildlife species that the proposed project is reasonably certain to cause. Based on the effects of the action analysis above, the Service anticipates that take in the form of accidental death, capture and relocation of boas, and take in the form of cutting of Higo chumbo cactus is likely to occur because of the proposed actions.

Mona boa

The principal area of concern for the Mona boa in relation to the effects of this project, is within and around Zone 5 tower site as well as the forested area through which the conduit will connect to the equipment in Zone 6. Zone 5 is approximately 0.32 acres (0.13 ha) of which 0.04 acre (0.016 ha) has not been previously disturbed (i.e., 12% of Zone 5). Outside of these zones, take of Mona boa is considered unlikely since those areas fall within the previously developed and disturbed camp and settlement are in Sardinera.

The rough estimate of the Mona boa is 120 boas per hectare in suitable habitat (Tolson 2000), giving, an estimate of approximately 16 boas or less that may occur in Zone 5, since most of the proposed tower site has been previously disturbed. Thus, the Service anticipates that no more than 16 Mona boa individuals will be incidentally taken for the duration of the project (4 months). This incidental take is expected to be in the form of injury or death (1 boa) and harassment and/or capture (15 boas) of Mona boas (all life stages) to prevent injury or death.

Higo chumbo

Based on the information provided for this project and in our files, the Service anticipates that at least one Higo chumbo cactus may be found within the proposed project area and timeframe (i.e., 4 months). The principal area of concern for the Higo chumbo in relation to the effects of this project, is within and around Zone 5 tower site. Zone 5 is approximately 0.32 acres (0.13 ha) of which 0.04 acre (0.016 ha) has not been previously disturbed (i.e., 12% of Zone 5). Take of Higo

chumbo outside of Zone 5 should be unlikely. Outside of this zone, take of Higo chumbo cactus is considered unlikely since those areas fall within the previously developed and disturbed camp and settlement are in Sardinera.

The density estimate for Higo chumbo cactus is 0.001 cactus per square meter (Rojas-Sandoval and Meléndez-Ackerman 2013), that is, an estimate of one individual that may occur in Zone 5. Thus, the Service anticipates that at least one Higo chumbo within the 0.32 acres (0.13 ha) of Zone 5 will be incidentally taken for the duration of the project (4 months). However, if there are more Higo chumbo in that Zone 5 or any other, all individuals may need to be incidentally taken according to the description of the proposed action and because relocation of Higo chumbo is not a viable option for this species. If take is unavoidable, this incidental take is expected to be in the form of the permanent removal of individuals from the population.

5.1. Reasonable and Prudent Measures

The Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure(s) (RPMs) described in this section are necessary or appropriate to minimize impacts of incidental take caused by the actions.

RPM 1. The Service requires that ICE and its contractors ensure projects are conducted and operated as designed, planned, documented, and reported.

RPM 2. The Service requires that ICE and its contractors follow Terms and Conditions below while capturing, handling, transporting, temporary holding, and relocating Mona boas to minimize the risk of injury and mortality to the species.

5.2. Terms and Conditions

In order for the exemption from the take prohibitions of §9(a)(1) and of regulations issued under §4(d) of the ESA to apply to the Action, ICE must comply with the terms and conditions (T&Cs) of this statement, provided below, which carry out the RPMs described in the previous section. These T&Cs are mandatory. As necessary and appropriate to fulfill this responsibility, ICE must require any permittee, contractor and recipient to implement these T&Cs through enforceable terms that the Federal Agency include in the permit or contract document.

T&C 1 (RPM 1). The Service and the Federal Agency will ensure take levels do not exceed levels anticipated in this BO.

1. Inform all project personnel about the potential presence of the Mona boa and Higo chumbo cactus in areas where the proposed work will be conducted. Conduct a pre-construction to inform all project personnel about the need to avoid harming these species and properly identify them as well.
2. Prior to any construction activity, including helicopter transport, staging, demolition, removal of vegetation, grading and earth movements, the boundaries of the project area and areas to be excluded and avoided will be clearly marked in the project plan and in the field in order to avoid further habitat degradation outside of the AA.

3. Do not use netting or geotextile fabric to stabilize vegetation in fragile areas as recommended. This will avoid any potential entanglement with the plants and animals in Mona.
4. ICE must develop and implement a biosecurity plan that includes protocols designed to protect island ecosystems from the threat of invasive species (IC 2016), particularly the *Harrisia cactus mealybug* and the green iguana (*Iguana iguana*).
5. Once areas are clearly marked, and prior to transporting materials to Zone 5 with the helicopter (Phase 0), a qualified biologist or designated project personnel able to identify Higo chumbo cactus will survey the project area to determine if any Higo chumbo are present with the AA, including adults, juveniles, and seedlings. If any Higo chumbo are observed within areas that may be affected by the project, the location of the cacti will be communicated to project personnel, and a buffer will be established to prevent the storage of equipment and foot traffic near the cacti. As specified in the BA, if cacti are identified on sites where vegetation will be cleared, additional consultation will be initiated with the Service and the DNER to determine how to best limit adverse effects to the cacti, which may include shifting the project footprint to avoid the cacti. If take is unavoidable, the individual(s) that will be affected should be measured and photographed to include that information in the take report for Higo chumbo.
6. The recommended use of netting or geotextile fabric to stabilize vegetation in fragile areas shall not be used due to potential entanglements with the plants and animals of Mona including the Mona boa.
7. ICE must develop a Mona boa survey and relocation plan in coordination with the Service. Before any activity that may affect the species (any staging, demolition, removal of vegetation, grading and earth movements), a qualified biologist(s) or designated project personnel with experience searching and handling snakes will survey areas during the day and night to capture and relocate boas out of harm's way. The principal area of concern for the Mona boa in relation to the effects of this project, is within and around Zone 5 tower site as well as the forested area through which the conduit will connect to the equipment in Zone 6. Once areas are clearly marked, and prior to activities that may affect the species the designated person(s) will conduct diurnal surveys to verify the presence of any Mona boa within the work area. Due to the species low detectability, the Mona boa will be searched at least three nights (and subsequent nights as needed) prior to any activity that may affect the species. Boas will be searched from 7:00-7:30 PM to at least 10:00 PM and proceed according to the T&C if a boa is found for capture and relocation (refer to T&C 2). Ideally at least two persons would search for Mona boas per night.
8. Once activities that may affect the species begin, the biologist or designated personnel must always be accessible and be ready to capture and relocate Mona boas that might be in harm's way as the result of the disturbance.
9. Prior to removal of vegetation the area is surveyed for Mona boas accordingly, vegetation will be cut with hand tools about one meter above ground prior to the use of heavy

machinery for land clearing and grading. Cutting vegetation by hand should allow Mona boas not detected during surveys to move away on their own to adjacent available habitat and discourage other boas from entering the area.

10. For all boa sightings (dead or alive), record the time and date of the sighting and the specific location where it was found, as well as the size, weight and sex (if possible) of the animal. Data will also include a photo of the animal (dead or alive), relocation site GPS coordinates, the time and date of the relocation, and comments on how the animal was detected and its behavior. Any dead boas found shall be collected and frozen as soon as possible in double plastic bags and properly identified. Information shall be written in pencil and waterproof paper and put inside the bag as well. Please record the collectors' name, date, GPS coordinates, and any additional relevant notes. When possible, the frozen specimens can be transferred to the Service or transported directly to the University of Puerto Rico Mayagüez campus herpetological collection at the Department of Biology (Service can provide further contact info).
11. If any Mona boa (dead or alive) that is found within the AA and on harm's way, the action will stop in that area and information recorded accordingly. All attempts will be made to immediately safely capture the animal (refer to T&C 2). Boas will be safely captured and relocated at least 1km within suitable habitat (forested) and away from construction areas. Relocation sites should be pre-determined before the project starts and shared with the Service for revision and concurrence. Relocation of Mona boas will be conducted by the biologist(s) or designated personnel and will not harm or injure the captured boa. Temporary holding (24 hours) of the captured individual may be needed if immediate relocation is not possible (refer to T&C 2).
12. Measures will be taken to avoid and minimize Mona boa casualties within any machinery (e.g. skid steer) and staging areas. Any machinery left on site and staging areas on or near Mona boa habitat must be thoroughly inspected each morning before work starts to ensure that no boas have sheltered within engine compartments or other areas of the machinery or staging areas. If a Mona boa is found within any of these, boas will be safely captured and relocated accordingly.
13. Mona boas may seek shelter within debris piles or other man-made structures. Measures should be taken to avoid and minimize boa casualties associated with sheltering in new debris piles or other man-made structures as a result of project activities. New debris piles should be placed in areas farthest away from forested areas. Prior to moving, disposing, or shredding, debris piles should be carefully inspected for the presence of Mona boas. If debris piles will be left on site, we recommend they be placed in an undisturbed area. In coordination with DNER, ICE may consider leaving vegetation debris piles on site if those will be left undisturbed for natural decomposition.
14. Should the form of take reach the amount of exempted take (one injured or dead boa, Section 5) during the proposed action, the Federal Agency and the Recipient shall terminate the authorized activities and contact the Service within 24 hours to reinstate consultation. The Service and the Federal Agency and the Recipient will re-consult to

determine whether authorized activities should continue as proposed and whether modifications or stipulations are warranted.

15. The appropriate contact information for the Service is:

- Felix López, Deputy Field Supervisor, email: felix_lopez@fws.gov, mobile: 305-304-1128
- Jan P. Zegarra, Fish & Wildlife Biologist, email: jan_zegarra@fws.gov, mobile: 939-320-3134

16. All reports must be submitted to caribbean_es@fws.gov, office #: 786-244-0081

T&C 2 (RPM 2). The Service requires ICE to follow standard procedures while capturing, handling, transporting, temporary holding, and relocating Mona boas in order to minimize the risk of injury and mortality to the species.

1. ICE must ensure that any contractors or cooperators follow proper procedures and methods for capturing, handling, temporary holding, and relocating Mona boas. The following procedures will be followed:
 - a. All Mona boas shall be handled safely to avoid injury. The Mona boa is a relatively small non-venomous snake considered easy to handle and relatively tame. The preferred method of capture is by hand, although a snake hook or stick may also be used if snake is uncatchable by hand, or to help move the snake into a safer position for capture.
 - b. All Mona boas may be temporarily held during and/or relocation purposes. Boas will be handled as little as possible, and they shall not be kept for more than 24 hours since the day of capture. Temporary holding of boas will be in burlap bags (1 boa per bag) and/or secured containers, which must be placed in cool dry areas that are not in direct sunlight or extreme temperatures. Burlap bags shall be placed inside a container with other boas each inside their own burlap bag and labeled properly. All containers shall be well-ventilated and with a secure lid to avoid boas from escaping.
 - c. ICE and its contractors shall obtain all necessary permit(s) from the corresponding State agency for capturing, handling, transporting, temporary keeping, and relocating Mona boas.

6. CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

§7(a)(1) of the ESA directs Federal agencies to use their authorities to further the purposes of the ESA by conducting conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary activities that an action agency may undertake to avoid or minimize the adverse effects of a proposed action, implement recovery plans, or develop information that is useful for the conservation of listed species.

We have not identified actions the Service could take on a programmatic basis, to address

Section 7(a)(I) that are not part of its normally mandated mission. However, previous projects have incorporated conservation measures and scientific research for the Mona boa and Higo chumbo cactus. In coordination with the Service and the DNER, additional conservation measures from those specified by ICE and in the Terms and Conditions could be implemented during the actions covered by this Biological Opinion. We provide the following conservation recommendations:

- To the maximum extent possible, minimize impacts from the helicopter flights particularly when flying to and from Zone 5. Flight path should avoid any transits over the plateau except for access to Zone 5.
- A native vegetation reforestation plan can be considered in Zone 5 and other areas where the existing vegetation will be cut and left to recover on its own to minimize growth of invasive grasses or other plants that may degrade the habitat in those areas.

7. Reinitiation Notice

This concludes formal consultation on the action(s) outlined in the (request/reinitiation request). As provided in 50 CFR §402.16, reinitiation of formal consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency, where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained (or is authorized by law) and if: (1) the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded; (2) new information reveals effects of the agency action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not considered in this opinion; (3) the agency action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat not considered in this opinion; or (4) a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the action. In instances where the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded, any operations causing such take must cease pending reinitiation.

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